

Can uncertainties in the evolution of massive stars explain properties of gravitational wave progenitors?

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Stars more massive than $9 M_{\odot}$ are known as massive stars. These stars are responsible for the chemical enrichment of the interstellar medium and are progenitors of many astrophysical phenomena such as supernovae, gamma-ray bursts and compact binary mergers. Recent observations such as the detection of gravitational waves from the merger of their remnants, neutron stars and black holes, have renewed interest in exploring the lives of these stars.

However, the evolution of these massive stars is riddled with uncertainties. These stars are born less often and spend only a few million years burning nuclear fuel, hence it is difficult to get observational constraints on their evolution. Therefore, several physical properties such as the mass-loss rates, nuclear reaction rates, and internal mixing processes remain uncertain for these stars. As a result, modellers have to make certain assumptions about these parameters while modelling the evolution of these stars with one-dimensional (1D) stellar evolution codes.

Numerical instabilities in the envelopes of massive stars

The evolution of stars more massive than $40 M_{\odot}$ is further complicated by the presence of sub-surface opacity bumps in their outer layers. Such massive stars are extremely bright with luminosities close to the critical Eddington luminosity required to balance outward radiation pressure with the inward gravitational pressure. In the low-density envelope of these stars, convection, as given by the mixing length theory [1], is inefficient, and the presence of elemental opacity bumps can cause the radiative luminosity to exceed the Eddington luminosity.

To maintain hydrostatic equilibrium, the density and gas pressure, which normally decrease with radius, increase locally in sub-surface layers, forming density and gas pressure inversions. These density inversions present a challenge while modelling the evolution of massive stars. The time-steps of the simulation become exceedingly small, and it becomes computationally challenging to model the further evolution of the star [2]. Therefore, modellers have to employ certain techniques, such as enhancing mass-loss rates to remove problematic outer layers or increasing convective efficiency by setting the mixing length proportional to the density scale height, to push forward the evolution of massive stars beyond these numerical instabilities.

Comparing massive star models from various codes

The combination of the different techniques to overcome numerical instabilities and the various physical uncertainties in the evolution of massive stars can result in large differences in the stellar models between different codes.

To determine the impact of these physical and numerical uncertainties on the evolutionary properties of massive stars, we compared non-rotating models of stars with initial masses between $9\text{--}200 M_{\odot}$, at near-solar metallicity from five different codes: models from the PAdova and TRieste Stellar Evolution Code (PARSEC; [3]), MESA Isochrones and Stellar Tracks (MIST; [4]) from the Modules for Experiments in Stellar Astrophysics (MESA; [5]), models [6] from the Geneva code [7], models from the Binary Population and Spectral Synthesis (BPASS; [8]), and the Bonn Optimized Stellar Tracks (BoOST; [9]) from the ‘Bonn’ Code.

Figure 1: Mass of the stellar remnant versus the initial mass of the star as predicted by various stellar models.

We find that the evolutionary properties of massive stars can vary significantly between these models. For example, Figure 1 shows the remnant mass of the star as a function of its initial mass, as predicted by the different sets of stellar models. The remnant mass has been calculated using the prescription from [10], based on the final core mass and the final total mass of the star. Geneva models do not provide core masses and therefore they have not been included in this comparison. As shown in the figure, the remnant mass predictions can differ by $20 M_{\odot}$ between different stellar models. Moreover, while the maximum black hole mass predicted by BoOST, MIST and PARSEC models at this metallicity is more than $30 M_{\odot}$, the most massive black hole predicted by BPASS models is just $20 M_{\odot}$. These differences are important for various studies including predictions of gravitational wave properties from compact binary mergers. However, currently none of these models can be established as better or worse than the others.

Population Synthesis and METISSE

To test the impact of the various uncertainties in the evolution of massive stars on the properties of gravitational wave progenitors, one needs population synthesis codes – codes that can model populations of stars and the various interactions between them. However, many of these codes rely on using fitting formulae for calculating evolutionary parameters of individual stars. These formulae are derived using polynomial fits to a set of 1D stellar models, and need to be recalculated for different sets of stellar models. However, defining these formulae is an arduous task. To address this, we have developed the METHod of Interpolation for Single Star Evolution (METISSE; [11]) that uses interpolation within a grid of pre-computed 1D stellar models to calculate stellar parameters. It is an improvement over the commonly used Single Star Evolution (SSE; [12]) fitting formulae, as the use of interpolation allows the user to easily use different sets of 1D stellar models, computed with different input parameters.

Figure 2: Maximum stellar radii as a function of the initial mass of the star, as predicted by SSE, METISSE with MESA, and METISSE with BEC.

We tested METISSE with stellar models from MESA and the Bonn code (BEC) by calculating parameters for stars in the range of 9–100 M_{\odot} at one-tenth of solar metallicity. Figure 2 shows the maximum radial expansion achieved by these stars as a function of their initial mass, as predicted by METISSE. For reference, the maximum stellar radii calculated with SSE for the same masses and metallicity are also plotted. Similar to Figure 1, stars with initial masses above 40 M_{\odot} show a larger discrepancy ($\geq 1000 R_{\odot}$) in the maximum radial expansion compared to other, lower mass stars. These are again an order of magnitude lower than what SSE predicts. The radial expansion of a star is important for determining its interaction with a binary companion. Thus, the different radii predicted by different stellar models can have a significant impact on the mass transfer and binary properties of the stars, which are important for predicting the formation of compact binary systems whose merger can give rise to the gravitational waves.

Conclusions

Uncertainties in the evolution of massive stars can play a significant role in predicting their evolutionary properties. Advances in observations and three-dimensional simulations might help resolve these uncertainties in the future. Until then, tools like METISSE are crucial for testing the impact of these uncertainties on the properties of stellar populations.

References

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